

BIO-INDICATING MATTER

Environmental Sensing with Biomaterials Using Reversible Color Change

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KEYWORDS

Biosensing, pH Indication, Living Systems, Computational Thermodynamics, Human and Environmental Health

ABSTRACT

This research explores the potential between mycelium structures and bioplastic gel coatings to imbue architectural surfaces with sensing capabilities through color change. Harnessing the hybridization of responsive biomaterial systems, which support carbon-positive frameworks for architectural materials, holds promise for creating bio-intelligent systems that benefit both environmental and human health. Bio-Indicating Matter demonstrates pH-sensing in biomaterial research, exploring how architectural surfaces can serve as interfaces for indoor ecological sensing. Integrating color-changing bioplastics with indoor mycelium wall surfaces enables the detection of water damage and alerts to microbial activity, fostering proactive and intuitive responses to maintain indoor environmental quality. Expanding on the computational shaping of wall surfaces responsive to the thermodynamics of airflow, these hybrid biomaterial systems can effectively mitigate potential microbial growth on substrates by integrating material properties and surface geometry. The project aims to develop contamination-responsive landscapes within architectural systems, acknowledging the natural presence of microbes in indoor environments while focusing on mitigating harmful factors. It expands design opportunities for user interaction with indoor space dynamics and suggests the deliberate reintegration of natural processes within built environments. This paper offers a framework for shaping architectural biomaterial surfaces while promoting healthier indoor environments and attuning human intuition to intimate ecological processes through shape and color expression.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lichen receives all its nutrients from the surrounding air, serving as a natural indicator of ecosystem health (National Park Forests, n.d). Inspired by lichen's responsiveness, Bio-indicating Matter leverages pH-indication as a means of material sensing to aid in monitoring changes within indoor spaces, offering insights into environmental health. This approach builds human intuition about natural and ecological processes, situating architecture as an environmental steward, and promoting preventative care.

Maintaining healthy indoor environments poses numerous challenges, including air quality, material degradation, and water damage. Signs of such changes often manifest late and complicate maintaining a healthy interior biome. The Environmental Protection Agency (2024) highlights that while there is no standard for a “healthy” or “normal” indoor microbiome, it underscores the importance of controlling moisture and promptly addressing wet areas to mitigate microbial growth. This provides an opportunity for bio-indicating surfaces that integrate responsive materials for healthier indoor spaces.

Current sustainability efforts in architectural research prioritize integrating regenerative materials and circular biomaterials. This study explores architecture's potential to engage in dynamic bio-responsive behaviour, proposing co-creating biosynthetic environments with pH-responsive biomaterials. Inspired by the teachings of Robin Wall Kimmerer (2013), an author and botanist who emphasizes ecological consciousness through careful awareness of the natural world, this research aligns with the view that paying attention to hyperlocal phenomena can educate us about larger ecological networks. In the Anthropocene, where climate change feels larger than life, Kimmerer's teachings highlight the importance of understanding and responding to local ecological signals.

Bio-indicating Matter leverages pH indication as a means of material sensing to aid in monitoring environmental changes within indoor spaces. By integrating non-toxic pH indicators with biomaterials and observing them in conjunction with local biomes, this research aims to develop pollution-responsive architectural surfaces. A deeper understanding of indoor environmental health and pollution can be achieved through material research and prototyping with biomaterials, ultimately driving the expression of bioindication as an aesthetic language. This approach builds human intuition about natural and ecological processes, situates architecture as an environmental steward, and promotes preventative care for indoor spaces.

Figure 1:
From top to bottom: Three captured stages of bioplastic coating colour change integrated with mycelium tile reacting to pH-based environmental stimuli for water damage and microbial sensing.

2. BACKGROUND

Bio-indicating Matter expands the capabilities of biomaterials and thermodynamics by responding to indoor temperature changes, connecting environmental health with architectural systems that adapt biological behaviour. “Sensing” in this study involves both a material’s response to environmental changes (Hossain, 2024) and evoking people’s sensory impressions that deepen material reflections (Material Pathways, 2020). This research argues for the integration of both bio-sensing to exist in a predominantly digital sensing environment.

Biomaterials are made from natural resources through processes that support a circular lifecycle, offering alternatives to fossil fuel-based materials. Mycelium-based composites, derived from the root structure of mushrooms, have emerged in the last decade as a plausible enhancement of industrial design and architectural products (Ecovative, n.d). According to research, mycelium has high insulation properties, which could lead to future indoor surfacing applications (Girometta, 2019). However, exploration into integrating sensing capabilities into mycelium remains limited.

A key literature review includes Kan et al. (2017), who used non-toxic plant extracts from anthocyanin pigments to vanillin to design pH-

reactive materials, thus significantly contributing to biomaterial sensing. Although much of this research focused on product use, little attention was directed toward architectural facades that could indicate mildew, water, or air pollutants.

Beckett's (2023) exploration of probiotic design explores hosting microbial communities within architectural materials as pathogen inhibitors. Through experiments with concrete, ceramics, nylon, and aluminium, Beckett demonstrated that building materials embedded with beneficial microbial functions can thrive without regular maintenance. Beckett's computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations further explore the relationship of the airflow-carrying microbial matter, either free or attached to dust.

Additionally, Kuka et al.'s (2022) work contextualizes indoor mold growth conditions and prevention strategies relative to temperature gradients along wall surfaces. The findings of the paper suggest that environmental conditions, particularly temperature and relative humidity, play crucial roles in mold growth on surfaces, with spore contamination and wood moisture content further influencing the process. In settings without artificial mold inoculation, the presence of spores significantly affects mold growth rates at lower temperatures (10 and 20 °C), while its impact diminishes at higher temperatures (30 °C).

Cupkova et al.'s *Sentient Concrete* (2018) explores how users can engage with the invisible workings of thermal comfort and indoor temperature variation through real-time sensing and color indication embedded within architectural radiant surfaces, facilitated through surface figuration that changes the heat transfer coefficient. The proposed concept of "architecture as a mood ring" moves away from the bias embedded in the engineering approach to mechanical systems, which is based on the quantitative average of metabolic range on narrow user demographics. Instead, it explores how thermal gradients, and human comfort can be coupled with thermochromic color patterns attuned to human consciousness. This approach aims to create a holistic environment that responds dynamically to its inhabitants and raises questions about the role of architecture as a naturalized medium for enhancing building performance through increased awareness of human diversity.

Kuka et al.'s study, complemented by Cupkova et al.'s (2017) et al.'s (2017) research on the thermodynamic consequences of surface figuration relative to the rate of thermal transfer, opens the opportunity to choreograph nuanced thermal gradients of building surfaces through the shaping of thermal zones conditioned towards specified temperature and humidity variations. The variations of wall surface articulation in its pattern scale and orientation can enhance relative airflow and thus affect mold growth rates. Together, these works suggest opportunities to manipulate surface thermal gradients to enhance airflow, thereby reducing relative humidity and potentially inhibiting microbial growth.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology includes pH indication through a cross-scalar framework comprising material research, computational design, and material prototyping, as a proof of concept. The process is structured into three phases: (a) Micro (Bioplastic Biosensing Capabilities), (b) Meso (Substrate Integration), and (c) Macro (Shaping System Design towards Environmental Health). The goal is to integrate material behaviour into a synthetic architectural system that reveals indoor water, microbial, and air changes (Figure 2).

The proof of concept through prototyping focuses on scaling up the naturalized behaviour of bioplastic pH indication at the micro-scale to identify and color-indicate a range of possible detections. At the mesoscale, the emphasis is on integrating the material substrate for bioplastic coatings with recycled building waste and mycelium. The macro-scale strategies incorporate knowledge from thermodynamics to shape wall patterns that allow for more effective signalling of microbial damage.

Figure 2: Methodology Diagram from Micro to Macro.

3.1. MICRO: BIOPLASTIC BIOSENSING CAPABILITIES

Non-toxic pH-responsive pigments known as anthocyanins (Khoo et al. 2017) are isolated from radish skin, red cabbage, and butterfly peas to assess color change strength and bioindication effectiveness. Pigment extraction involves boiling each plant in distilled water for half an hour and then sieving the mixture. A pH-neutral bioplastic is created using 200ml water, 7g Kappa Carrageenan, and 2.5ml glycerine, resulting in varying colors depending on the pigment: purple (red cabbage), light pink (radish), and blue (butterfly pea).

Figure 3 depicts the reactivity of anthocyanin-pigmented bioplastic. Initial samples are neutral (pH 7) and change color locally when exposed to acids (pH 2) or alkaline (pH 8-8.5). Acidic tests using lemon juice in an eyedropper deposit a center dot, shifting to deep pink

(radish), hot pink (red cabbage), and light pink (butterfly pea). Alkaline tests result in a second ring, displaying purple (radish), deep green (red cabbage), and light green (butterfly pea). Over time, some of the samples' alkaline rings change color from purple to green or yellow.

The range of pH reactions is tested with 1 tablespoon of lemon juice (pH 2; Petre 2023) and 1 teaspoon of baking soda dissolved in a cup of water (pH 8-8.5; Armand Hammer n.d). According to the research, pigments turn yellow when exposed to strong alkalines with a pH of 13/14 (Yi 2012). The cause of the color change has yet to be identified because these samples were not subjected to strong alkalis. The experiment validates the reviewed literature regarding the color change in each anthocyanin type (Saptarini 2015; Abedi-Firozjah 2022; Yi 2023). The color change is unique to the varying plants from which the anthocyanin was derived, building a palette of colors.

Figure 3: Different anthocyanin pigments embedded into bioplastics, color changes resulting from exposure to acidic and alkaline conditions.

Reversibility of bioplastic color change is critical for indoor bio-sensing. While coatings can be reapplied after damage, addressing reversibility is key to prolonging the performance and reducing waste. The bioplastics' reversibility to the original colors after pH exposure is tested using water and counter pH solutions. Applying water to the dry bioplastic surface of mycelium removes pigment from the bioplastic. This technique would require countless reapplications, which is not sustainable in the long-term use.

In contrast, the counter-PH testing reversed the color change by applying the opposite pH of what had stained the bioplastic. The tests were successful at reversing the color change, provided the solutions were strategically applied within the bounds of the changed bioplastic to avoid affecting neutral areas (Figure 4).

PIGMENT COATING

BIOPLASTIC COATING

Figure 4:
Reversibility tests of pigment coating in contrast to bioplastic coating.

We conducted observational studies to assess the bioplastic pH changes under various environmental conditions such as water damage to a wall surface, air quality changes, and microbial growth. Initial tests, focusing on indicating water damage, involve a neutral bioplastic dyed with either both or single pH-2 and pH-8 indicators (Figure 5). After being left to dry, water is re-applied to the bioplastic surface (Figure 5, 0-2 Day Sample), on median-aged bioplastic (Figure 5, 2-14 Day Sample), and aged bioplastic (Figure 5, 14+ Day Sample). The results indicate that newer bioplastic samples transition from alkaline to neutral, whereas aged bioplastics remain unchanged due.

All three experiments demonstrate a positive shift from acidic to neutral upon water exposure, with aged samples performing best. This suggests that acidic-coated or embedded bioplastics can effectively signal water transitions from acidic to neutral (Figure 5).

Red cabbage-based anthocyanins respond to air pollutants, as Romao et al. (2023) indicate red cabbage dye is sensitive to ammonia and similar bases. During tests with cleaning agents, the bioplastic shifts from neutral to alkaline (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Environmental sensing results were conducted with water, air, and microbial changes.

It also responds to mold, changing from purple to red, suggesting fungal release of acidic compounds. Given the usage of red cabbage pigments in food packaging to detect spoiling (Hassanpour, 2022), it is reasonable to assume that mold changes the pH of the hydrogel. These findings support pH-based bioindication as an effective method for detecting environmental pollutants from water, air, and microbes (Figure 5).

3.2. MESO: SUBSTRATE INTEGRATION

Bio-indicating Matter incorporates computational shaping to determine the area of bio-indications on wall surfaces through a bioplastic coating. This method expands on the computational workflow of ecological shape-making using image-based depth mapping (Cupkova, 2022) to enhance the effectiveness of biomaterial placement and substrate integration.

Two material systems—mycelium composite and recycled gypsum—are tested for bioplastic integration, focusing on circularity and adaptability for indoor use. These substrates are chosen to provide a range of synthetically derived and natural bio-based indoor products.

A substrate integration framework (Figure 6) tracks material characteristics, comparing environmental, aesthetic, and physical properties (Ashby, 2012). Additional qualities were added to track bioindication effects, such as sensing vs. static and synthetic vs. natural. Material experiments undergo iterative testing to enhance performance (Figure 7).

ENVIRONMENTAL TESTS

OBJECTIVES

Figure 6: Material Characteristics and qualities of substrate compared in material exploration

Characterization involves hybridizing bioplastic with substrates using computationally derived shapes to assess surface figuration, considering substrate thickness and bioplastic spread. Small-scale studies are designed to understand how shape and material integration affect bioplastic behaviour. Substrate shaping enhances the integration of the materials due to bioplastic shrinkage.

Preliminary tests using PLA and powder-based 3D prints (Figure 7) test bioplastic integration at different thicknesses. The findings show that the shaping of surfaces with varying figuration allows for consistent and even layers of biomaterial integration with the substrate due to shrinkage ratios. These tests determine the shaping strategy for the formation of pockets and valleys in material samples, which serve as positives for molding mycelium and gypsum that are subsequently coated with bio-indicating bioplastic. This shaping strategy demonstrates its scalability to the macro-scale, enabling thermodynamic considerations to guide airflow across the vertical wall surface.

Figure 7: Material explorations of bio indicating bioplastic compatibility with substrate and shaping characteristics.

GYPSUM

MYCELIUM

BIOPLASTIC

Gypsum substrate testing focused on using recycled gypsum powder, molded with bioplastic as a binder or as a coating. The alkalinity of gypsum interferes with bioplastic, turning them blue. Additional coating types were explored to address the interference; however, only PLA-based coatings were successful (Figure 7, top-left). In contrast, mycelium substrates did not interfere with the identifiable bioplastic color change. This led to an exploration of various layers of anthocyanin pigments from butterfly peas and red cabbage.

Figure 8: Material explorations of bio-indicating bioplastic compatibility with substrate and shaping characteristics.

A 1:1 scale prototype explored substrate compatibility and fabrication efficiency with mycelium and gypsum. The bioplastic coating turns blue when applied to gypsum substrate, (Figure 8) but remains neutral when applied to mycelium. Gypsum casting is labor-intensive yet yields high-fidelity curvature due to its curing process. Mycelium casting, a simpler two-step process, is prone to shrinkage, thus affecting resolution. Deeper mold curves can offset this shrinkage. Mycelium composites excel as bio-indicating hybrids, avoiding pH conflicts and supporting biocompatible adhesion.

3.3. MACRO: SYSTEMS DESIGN AND ENVIRONMENTAL

The macroscale design framework combines pH-sensitive bioplastic integrated with mycelium composites using computational shaping relative to thermal flow, creating a wall prototype to reduce microbial growth. Environmental conditions, such as relative humidity and temperature, affect mold growth on surfaces. Kuka et al.'s (2022) research suggests that by decreasing temperature and relative humidity it takes mold a longer time to develop. By gradually increasing air pockets between natural airflow and the wall geometry (Cupkova et al., 2017) the proposed wall surface shaping choreographs the rate of thermal exchange, regulated through natural convection to higher relative humidity within discrete parts of surfaces.

Beckett's (2021) research shows that smooth, low rugosity surface textures reduce microbial growth. Our design framework combines shaping with smooth texturing and uses moisture-resistant mycelium tiles (Tacer-Kaba 2020) to reduce microbial growth.

Figure 9: Illustrated from left to right: The background research on how computationally designed wall pockets can alter airflow across a surface and the relationship between mold germination and temperature, followed by the thermal gradient design and its application onto the wall using bioindicating bioplastics.

The design framework integrates biomaterial studies through modular tiles (Figure 9). Since water damage and moisture retention are leading factors for mold growth, such geometric figuration would enable more effective detection of changes due to water damage and microbial growth. This is accomplished by layering acidic and neutral bioplastics at different surface heights within a single tile. An acidic pH indicates water damage, while a neutral pH signals microbial growth.

Our proposed material system would suit various collective spaces like gyms or educational centers with shared microbial environments. In Figure 10, the damage is simulated through a color indication from left to right. Initially, the bioplastic's bottom layer turns purple from water exposure. While reversible, improper treatment leads to early signs of microbial growth, indicated by pink bioplastic on the right. This timescape (Figure 10) illustrates interactions that facilitate communication between humans and their environments, promoting intuitive, preventative care for indoor spaces. It demonstrates how pH-indicating landscapes facilitate human-environment interaction, encouraging proactive care for indoor spaces.

Figure 10a:
 Simulated application of wall surface: initially showing an unaffected wall indicating water damage, then reversed to show microbial damage.

Figure 10b:
 Simulated application of wall surface: initially showing an unaffected wall indicating water damage, then reversed to show microbial damage.

4. DISCUSSION

This material research contributes to dynamic, responsive systems with bioindicating properties, using a holistic shaping strategy to create locally reactive conditions indoors. The multiscale approach explores the interaction of pH-altering bioplastics with environmental changes over time. At the microscale, material research demonstrates that pH sensors can be integrated into indoor environments to detect moisture and microbial growth. Mesoscale prototypes show how pH-sensing bioplastics are incorporated into biomaterials like mycelium, as they are neutral substrates, further supporting the integration of material circularity, environmental health, and human-ecological intuition. At the macroscale, a computational design approach shapes wall surfaces in response to principles of thermodynamics to drive more air movement, potentially reducing microbial growth.

Figure 11:
**Projected Visual impact of
bio-indicating bioplastic
integrated on mycelium tiles.**

Bio-indicating Matter proposes that architectural surfaces embedded with pH-sensing materials can serve as early bioindicators of environments conducive to human health, fostering proactive care of indoor spaces by detecting changes in moisture and contamination. Future research should explore focused studies on assessing long-term and repeated bacterial growth and surface indication methods relative to material weathering, combined with computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations to analyze interactions between indoor airflows and the walls. Strategies such as reducing the alkalinity of gypsum surfaces, integrating pH-sensitive bioplastics, and employing hydrophobic bioplastics could enhance compatibility with alkaline substrates.

The research contributes to the theme of responsive cities and habitation by emphasizing the critical role that architecture plays in forming abiotic and biotic ecosystems across scales. Bio-indicating Matter emphasizes the importance of surface topology in deterring microbial growth while signaling its presence. The findings advocate for bio-intelligent environments that integrate natural and constructed systems with human intuition through bioindicator materials capable of monitoring and adapting to environmental changes. This approach encourages adaptable, preventative care by converting architectural surfaces into interactive extensions of invisible moisture, microbial, and air conditions.

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